

Preliminary investigations into the hydrodynamic performance of lift-based wave energy converters

P. Lamont-Kane, M. Folley, C. Frost and T. Whittaker

Abstract—¹ The majority of devices designed to extract energy from ocean waves operate through exploitation of the buoyancy (Froude-Krylov) and/or diffraction force regimes. Such devices extract energy through interaction with the displacement and/or acceleration of fluid particle motions respectively. By comparison, very little consideration has been given to systems which extract wave energy through coupling with fluid particle velocities. This paper performs a preliminary investigation into the hydrodynamics of a Wave Energy Converter (WEC) that is driven through interaction with the wave-induced fluid particle velocity. In particular, the work focuses on lift-based WECs consisting of a number of wave-driven, rotating hydrofoils. The paper develops a mathematical framework for such a system operating in regular, linear waves in 2D. It is noted that despite the unique nature of the device, it is possible to represent its operation using mathematics which are already familiar to the wave energy sector. The mathematical framework is subsequently used to investigate the performance of a pair of wave-driven, rotating hydrofoils. Results show that power capture efficiencies up to approximately 80% are potentially possible for the particular system considered under the constraints assumed. It is also found that the system is relatively insensitive to variations in design and control conditions. This suggests that further investigation is warranted to determine if lift-based WECs might represent a reasonable means of wave energy extraction.

Keywords— hydrodynamics, lift-based wave energy converter, rotating hydrofoil, wave energy, wave energy converter

I. INTRODUCTION

SINCE the widespread generation of interest in wave energy in the mid-to-late 1970's, there has been sustained interest in the development of devices that can extract energy from ocean waves. To date, many

hundreds, if not thousands, of device concepts have been proposed. However, as yet, no particular device type has achieved commercial viability.

The vast majority of those WECs that have been developed have sought to extract wave energy through exploitation of either the buoyancy and/or diffraction force regimes. Such devices seek to generate driving forces through their interaction with the wave-induced fluid particle displacement and/or acceleration respectively.

In contrast, very few systems have been proposed which extract energy through interaction with the wave-induced fluid particle velocity (some examples of devices which have attempted this are presented in [1]). This was noted by Folley et al., 2019 [2], who highlighted a significant knowledge gap in the Wave Energy sector's understanding of velocity-driven systems. Folley et al. described a number of inherent advantages of velocity-driven WECs, and in particular, lift-based devices. Many of these advantages directly address issues which have frustrated traditional device types from achieving commercial viability, such as the difficulties associated with reciprocating motion and extreme wave loading. This suggests lift-based WECs that exploit wave-induced fluid particle velocities might represent a potential path to commercialisation of the wave energy sector.

Consequently, this paper conducts a preliminary investigation into the hydrodynamic performance of a lift-based WEC. In particular, the paper investigates a device consisting of a series of 2-dimensional, phase-locked, wave-driven, rotating hydrofoils. Phase-locking refers to the condition where the hydrofoils rotate at the same frequency as the incident waves and with a constant phase relationship to those waves. A basic mathematical framework describing the hydrodynamic performance of such a device comprised of any number of hydrofoils is developed in Section II. This framework is subsequently used to determine the maximum efficiency of a particular

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implementation of such a system in Section III. The paper closes with conclusions of the work presented in Section IV followed by a description of the ongoing and further works in Section V.

II. DEVELOPING THE MATHEMATICAL FRAMEWORK

This section develops a mathematical framework describing the hydrodynamics of a 2-dimensional lift-based WEC consisting of any number of rotating hydrofoils operating in linear, regular, surface water waves. Note this representation ignores second-order effects due to the finite amplitude of motion of the hydrofoil to provide greater clarity to the fundamental hydrodynamics governing system performance.

A. The operation of a wave-driven, rotating hydrofoil

There are many ways a device could be designed to extract energy from ocean waves through interaction with wave-induced fluid particle velocities. However, it is expected that the generation of lift by one or more hydrofoils that rotate with the wave in a phase-locked manner likely represents one of the more promising solutions. In the alternative, this will at least provide a useful starting point that may later be used as a benchmark or reference point for comparative assessment of future, more complex, systems.

To begin, consider the case of a simple hydrofoil where the incident velocity is composed of the velocity due to self-motion of the foil, u , coupled with a smaller velocity resulting from the surrounding fluid particle motions, v . The resultant is the relative fluid velocity, w , which acts at an angle of attack, α , relative to the chord line of hydrofoil. Under such conditions, both a lift force, F_L , and a drag force, F_D , will be generated as outlined in Figure 1.

Figure 1: The generation of lift and drag by a simple hydrofoil.

Now consider the case where the hydrofoil is free to rotate about a fixed point, O , and is held at a given radius, R , from that point. If the system is placed beneath the free water surface, then it can be driven by wave-based orbital particle motions of surface waves as outlined in Figure 2.

Furthermore, for the case of regular waves in deep water, if it is assumed that variation in the wave-induced fluid velocity is small across the swept area of the device, then for a phase-locked system (where the phase relationship between the wave and the body does not vary with time), the relative fluid velocity and angle of attack remain constant throughout the wave cycle. This means that the generation of lift is similarly constant, suggesting

maximum power capture can be obtained through time invariant control of variables such as hydrofoil phase, pitch, and operational radius for a given wave condition.

Note that Figure 2 represents a snapshot in time and includes representation of both the pitch of the hydrofoil, β , and its phase relative to the incident wave crest, ϕ .

Figure 2: Velocity-force diagram for a simple wave-driven, rotating hydrofoil. Not drawn to scale.

It is noted that the device described has superficial similarity to a number of other lift-based systems such as a Darrieus wind turbine, or crossflow turbine operating in unidirectional flow. However, in the case of a wave-driven hydrofoil, the inflow condition is rotational such that the angle of attack and angle to tangent (see below) remain constant throughout the wave cycle. This together with the effect of radiated waves limits potential for learning from other visually similar device types as the fundamental dynamics of the systems are inherently different.

B. Coordinate system and physical description

To develop the mathematical model, consider the case of n fully submerged hydrofoils, free to rotate in the x - z plane about a common fixed point, O , which is located at a depth, h , beneath the free water surface. Assume that each hydrofoil rotates about the point, O , at the same, constant radius, R , and has an independent, pre-defined fixed pitch, β_i , where the subscript, i , indicates the value for the i^{th} hydrofoil such that $i = \{1, 2, \dots, n\}$. If the hydrofoil is assumed to rotate in the same direction as the wave-driven fluid particle motions in a phase-locked manner, then the time invariant phase of each hydrofoil relative to the incident water wave can be described by, ϕ_i .

Assume that the system is driven by an incident sinusoidal surface water wave of amplitude, a , and angular frequency, ω , with surface elevation, ξ , given according to (1).

$$\xi(t) = a \sin(\omega t) \quad (1)$$

The position of a given hydrofoil, H_i , may be described using either cartesian (x_i, z_i) or polar (R_i, θ_i) coordinates. While Figure 2 depicts a single rotating hydrofoil, the framework developed permits representation of a system comprised of any number of hydrofoils with any combination of pitch and phase angles.

Finally, positive x is taken to the right, positive z is vertically upwards and rotation, θ , is positive anticlockwise from the positive x -axis. The incident wave travels from left to right in accordance with (1), driving anticlockwise rotation of the fluid particles. Consequently, the rotation of the wave-driven hydrofoils is also anticlockwise. To maintain consistency, pitch rotation (β) is also taken as positive in the anticlockwise direction.

C. Preparatory calculations & definitions

Calculation of the system's hydrodynamic efficiency requires expressions for a number of intermediary system characteristics. This section details those expressions.

Relative fluid velocity (w)

The relative fluid velocity, w , experienced by the hydrofoil results from the combination of the motion of the hydrofoil, u , and the depth-attenuated wave-induced fluid particle velocity, v' (see Figure 2).

If the hydrofoil is considered as a single discrete point, the cosine rule can be applied to the geometry of the velocity diagram to obtain an expression for the relative fluid velocity, w , as a function of u , v' and the hydrofoil phase relative to the wave, ϕ . Noting the assumptions of phase-locked motion and operation in regular waves, the wave-induced fluid velocity is $v' = a'\omega$ and the velocity of the hydrofoil is simply $u = R\omega$. Applying these results to the expression for w , and introducing a non-dimensional parameter, χ' , as the ratio of hydrofoil radius to the local amplitude of fluid particle motion, $\chi' = R/a'$, provides:

$$w^2 = a'^2 \omega^2 (1 + \chi'^2 - 2\chi' \cos \phi) \quad (2)$$

It is useful to non-dimensionalize this expression which yields the non-dimensional relative fluid velocity, \tilde{w} , defined as the ratio of the relative fluid velocity to the local wave-induced fluid velocity as shown by (3):

$$\tilde{w}^2 = \frac{w^2}{a'^2 \omega^2} = 1 + \chi_i'^2 - 2\chi_i' \cos \phi_i \quad (3)$$

While the system is driven by surface waves of amplitude, a , the wave-induced fluid velocity at the hydrofoil, a' , is diminished due to depth attenuation. Thus, a depth attenuation factor, Γ , may be defined as:

$$\Gamma = \frac{a'}{a} \quad (4)$$

For simplicity, the fluid particle amplitude experienced at the hydrofoil throughout the entirety of the hydrofoil rotation is assumed to be equal to that of the fluid particle amplitude at the depth of the fixed axis of rotation, h .

In the absence of pre-existing data for comparison, a first-pass assessment of this assumption's validity has been conducted. Performance efficiencies obtained using this method have been compared to those obtained as the average of using inflow velocities encountered at the top and bottom of the swept area (i.e., maximum and minimum inflow velocities). Deviation of results between is typically small (<10% deviation) except at very small wave periods which are unlikely to be encountered in any significant volume. As such, potential error is considered acceptable given the preliminary stage of investigations and the lack of significant impact up to 10% deviation is expected to have on the system's fundamental (governing) hydrodynamics, which is the primary focus of this work.

Angle of attack (α) & angle to tangent (α_0)

The angle of attack, α , is the angle that the relative fluid velocity vector makes with the chord line of the hydrofoil (Figure 2). The angle to tangent, α_0 , is the angle that the relative fluid velocity makes to the hydrofoil's instantaneous direction of travel. The angle to tangent is defined as the angle of attack plus the pitch angle and is used to determine the tangential and radial components of lift and drag forces generated by the hydrofoil. Both the angle of attack and angle to tangent will be constant for a phase-locked rotating hydrofoil moving in a circle under the action of regular waves, assuming no variation in other system variables such as phase, pitch, and radius.

Where the relative fluid velocity was obtained through use of the cosine rule, the angle to tangent, α_0 , is obtained from the application of the sine rule to the same velocity geometry, which, after some rearranging provides:

$$\alpha_0 = \sin^{-1} \left(\frac{\sin \phi}{\sqrt{(1 + \chi'^2 - 2\chi' \cos \phi)}} \right) \quad (5)$$

As the angle to tangent is simply the sum of the angle of attack, α , and the hydrofoil pitch, β , i.e. ($\alpha_0 = \alpha + \beta$) then the angle of attack, α , can be found from:

$$\alpha = \sin^{-1} \left(\frac{\sin \phi}{\sqrt{(1 + \chi'^2 - 2\chi' \cos \phi)}} \right) - \beta \quad (6)$$

Finally, it is useful to have an expression for the cosine of α_0 . Noting that $\cos(\sin^{-1}(x)) = \sqrt{1 - x^2}$, then:

$$\cos \alpha_0 = \sqrt{1 - \frac{\sin^2 \phi}{1 + \chi'^2 - 2\chi' \cos \phi}} \quad (7)$$

Incident wave power

The incident wave power per metre crest, P_i , in deep water is given by:

$$P_i = \frac{\rho g^2 a^2}{4\omega} \quad (8)$$

Radiation damping coefficient (B)

A commonly used tool to calculate the hydrodynamic (radiation) damping of a Wave Energy Converter is the Haskind Relation [3], [4]. The Haskind Relation shows that the radiation damping coefficient of an oscillating system can be calculated if the amplitude of the excitation force is known. Using the Haskind Relation, it can be shown [4] that for small oscillations in any of the traditional 6 degrees-of-freedom, the radiation damping coefficient for a 2-dimensional system can be calculated from:

$$B_j = \frac{\omega}{\rho g^2 a^2} |\hat{F}_j|^2 \quad (9)$$

Where B_j is the radiation damping coefficient in the j^{th} mode of motion, ρ is the density of the surrounding fluid, g is the acceleration due to gravity and \hat{F}_j is the complex amplitude of the excitation force in the j^{th} mode.

For the case of a phase-locked hydrofoil moving in a circle under regular waves with time-invariant control parameters, all local forces acting on the hydrofoil (in a reference frame moving with the hydrofoil) are fixed in time and thus the system will rotate with constant speed.

Radiation damping is defined as the hydrodynamic damping proportional to velocity. Thus, where the magnitude of velocity is constant, so too is the magnitude of the radiation damping force.

In order to determine the radiation damping coefficient of the hydrofoil when considered as a unidirectional rotating system, B_θ , it is useful to first consider the motion as a set of simultaneous oscillation in both heave and surge. When the device motion is considered as a combination of oscillations in both heave and surge, the average power loss due to radiation damping over a single cycle, $\langle P_B \rangle$, is given by:

$$\begin{aligned} \langle P_B \rangle &= \frac{1}{2\pi} \int_0^{2\pi} [B_x \omega^2 R^2 \sin^2(\phi - \theta) + \\ & B_z \omega^2 R^2 \cos^2(\phi - \theta)] d\theta \\ \gg \langle P_B \rangle &= \frac{1}{2} (B_x + B_z) \omega^2 R^2 \end{aligned} \quad (10)$$

Where, B_z and B_x are the radiation damping coefficients in heave and surge respectively and $\langle \cdot \rangle$ indicates the mean value of a quantity over a single cycle.

Consequently, as the power loss due to radiation damping for the unidirectionally rotating system is given by $B_\theta R^2 \omega^2$ (as shown below in Section II-D), the radiation damping coefficient for the rotating system, B_θ , is simply the average of the coefficients in heave and surge:

$$B_\theta = \frac{1}{2} (B_x + B_z) \quad (11)$$

Where, B_x and B_z are obtained from (9) using knowledge of the magnitude of the excitation force.

For the case of a single rotating hydrofoil, (the i^{th} hydrofoil) the excitation force is the tangential component

of the lift force, $F'_{L,i}$ driving the system forward. That is, $F'_{L,i} = F_{L,i} \sin \alpha_{0,i}$, which is invariant with time. This is both the magnitude of the driving force in the rotational frame of reference, and the amplitude of the driving forces in both the heave and surge modes when the system is considered in two oscillatory modes. Consequently, noting from (8) that $\omega/\rho g^2 a^2 = 1/4P_i$ then according to (9) the radiation damping coefficient for a rotating hydrofoil may be calculated from:

$$B_{ii} = \frac{F'_{L,i}{}^2}{4P_i} \quad (12)$$

This expression provides the radiation damping coefficient for a single, rotating hydrofoil. For a rotor of n hydrofoils operating at the same radius, the combined radiation damping coefficient for the entire rotor, B_θ , is given by (13) where F'_L is simply the summation of the excitation forces of all n hydrofoils (see (15) if necessary).

$$B_\theta = \frac{F'_L{}^2}{4P_i} \quad (13)$$

Note that the results presented in (12) and (13) only hold true for operation in a 2-dimensional environment. In fact, it has been found that for operation in a 3-dimensional wave environment, the radiation damping coefficient differs between the heave and surge modes due to differences in the radiation pattern in the two modes [5]. Furthermore, the referenced work suggests that in general, as a result of this finding, the optimum path of a rotating hydrofoil in deep water is not circular as may be expected, but rather, elliptical. This poses a number of interesting questions and implications for these types of device which are further discussed in the referenced work.

D. Instantaneous & average harmonic power capture

To simplify the mathematics, it is useful to treat the system of n hydrofoils as a single rotor. Then, the instantaneous power capture, $P_\theta(t)$, of any number of rotating hydrofoils considered as a single degree-of-freedom rotational system can be calculated as the cumulative power generated due to lift, minus the cumulative power lost due to drag, minus the power lost due to wave radiation by the rotor:

$$\begin{aligned} P_\theta(t) &= \sum_{i=1}^n F_{L,i}(t) \omega(t) R(t) \sin \alpha_{0,i}(t) - \\ & \sum_{i=1}^n F_{D,i}(t) \omega(t) R(t) \cos \alpha_{0,i}(t) - \\ & B_\theta R(t)^2 \omega(t)^2 \end{aligned} \quad (14)$$

Note that the instantaneous power capture, $P_\theta(t)$, is the power extracted from the system via the Power Take Off (PTO) unit and as such, the effect of the PTO on device response is inherent within the analysis.

As the system is phase locked, the angular velocity of the rotor is equal to that of the wave at any given time. Furthermore, operation in regular waves dictates that the

rotational velocity of the system will be constant in time such that $\dot{\theta}(t) = \omega(t) = \omega$.

Under such conditions, and assuming any change in the wave-induced fluid velocity, v' , is small across the swept area, then there is no requirement to alter the control variables of radius, pitch and phase in time. Maximum, or any other given level, of power capture can be obtained via time-invariant specification of the control parameters such that optimisation is achievable on a per-wave-state basis. Finally, recall from the previous section (*Section II C: Radiation Damping Coefficient*) that the radiation damping coefficient in 2-dimensions is constant throughout the rotational cycle. Now for ease of inspection, it is helpful to make the following definitions.

$$F'_L = \sum_{i=1}^n F_{L,i} \sin \alpha_{0,i} \quad (15)$$

$$F'_D = \sum_{i=1}^n F_{D,i} \cos \alpha_{0,i} \quad (16)$$

Under the conditions described above, and incorporating the definitions given in (15) and (16), the expression for instantaneous power capture given in (14) simplifies to expression (17).

$$P_\theta(t) = F'_L R \omega - F'_D R \omega - B_\theta R^2 \omega^2 \quad (17)$$

As expected, due to the quasi steady-state nature of the system resulting from its phase-locked operation in regular waves, the equation for the instantaneous power capture contains no time-dependent terms. Thus, the mean power capture over a single wave cycle is simply:

$$\begin{aligned} \langle P_\theta \rangle &= \frac{1}{T} \int_0^T P_\theta(t) dt \\ \gg \langle P_\theta \rangle &= F'_L R \omega - F'_D R \omega - B_\theta R^2 \omega^2 \end{aligned} \quad (18)$$

E. Efficiency of a series of 2D rotating hydrofoils

The hydrodynamic efficiency of the system is simply defined as its average power capture over the incident wave power:

$$\eta = \frac{\langle P_\theta \rangle}{P_i} \quad (19)$$

Recalling the expression for $\langle P_\theta \rangle$ from (18), then (19) may be written as:

$$\eta = \frac{F'_L R \omega (1 - \epsilon) - B_\theta R^2 \omega^2}{P_i} \quad (20)$$

Where ϵ is the nondimensional ratio of tangential drag to tangential lift forces ($\epsilon = F'_D / F'_L$).

Substituting in the results for the radiation damping coefficient, B_θ , and the incident wave power, P_i , from (13) and (8) respectively, then with simplification (20) becomes:

$$\eta = \frac{4F'_L R \omega^2}{\rho g^2 a^2} (1 - \epsilon) - \frac{4F'_L{}^2 R^2 \omega^4}{\rho^2 g^4 a^4} \quad (21)$$

Now, the lift, $F_{L,i}$, and drag, $F_{D,i}$, forces in a 2-dimensional environment for a given hydrofoil can be found from:

$$F_{L,i} = \frac{1}{2} \rho C_i w_i^2 C_{L,i} \quad (22)$$

$$F_{D,i} = \frac{1}{2} \rho C_i w_i^2 C_{D,i} \quad (23)$$

Where, C_i is the chord length of a given hydrofoil. The term w_i^2 is the square of the relative fluid velocity experienced by the i^{th} hydrofoil and is obtained from (2). Finally, $C_{L,i}$ and $C_{D,i}$ are the coefficients of lift and drag respectively for the i^{th} hydrofoil and are dependent on the angle of attack, α_i , experienced by that foil.

Using the expression for w^2 presented in (2), and recalling the expression for \tilde{w}^2 given in (3), then (22) and (23) can be used to expand (15) and (16) respectively into:

$$F'_L = \frac{1}{2} \rho a'^2 \omega^2 \sum_{i=1}^n C_i \tilde{w}_i^2 C_{L,i} \sin \alpha_{0,i} \quad (24)$$

$$F'_D = \frac{1}{2} \rho a'^2 \omega^2 \sum_{i=1}^n C_i \tilde{w}_i^2 C_{D,i} \cos \alpha_{0,i} \quad (25)$$

Using these results, the expression for the term, ϵ , can be expanded, and is given in (29). In addition, using a rearrangement of the result presented in (5), (24) can be further expanded to yield:

$$F'_L = \frac{1}{2} \rho a'^2 \omega^2 \sum_{i=1}^n C_i \tilde{w}_i C_{L,i} \sin \phi_i \quad (26)$$

Note: the non-dimensional relative fluid velocity, \tilde{w}_i , is no longer squared (see (26) vs (24)) due to the relationship between the angle to tangent, $\alpha_{0,i}$, and the phase angle, ϕ_i .

Finally, knowing that $k_o = \omega^2 / g$, then substituting the results from (24), (25) and (26) into (21) gives an expression for the efficiency of a 2-dimensional lift-based WEC consisting of any number of rotating hydrofoils:

$$\eta = 2\zeta(1 - \epsilon) - \zeta^2 \quad (27)$$

Where:

$$\zeta = R k_o^2 \Gamma^2 \sum_{i=1}^n C_i \tilde{w}_i C_{L,i} \sin \phi_i \quad (28)$$

$$\epsilon = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n C_i \tilde{w}_i^2 C_{D,i} \cos \alpha_{0,i}}{\sum_{i=1}^n C_i \tilde{w}_i^2 C_{L,i} \sin \alpha_{0,i}} \quad (29)$$

Note that expressions which permit calculation of the depth attenuation factor, Γ , the non-dimensional relative fluid velocity, \tilde{w}_i , the cosine of the angle to tangent, $\cos \alpha_{0,i}$, and the sine of the angle to tangent, $\sin \alpha_{0,i}$, can be found in (4), (3), (7) and (5) respectively.

III. THE HYDRODYNAMIC PERFORMANCE OF A LIFT-BASED WAVE ENERGY CONVERTER

This section uses the mathematical framework developed in Section II to conduct a preliminary investigation into the hydrodynamic performance of a 2-dimensional lift-based WEC operating in regular waves. Whilst this may not provide a complete understanding of the real-world potential of such a device, it does provide a starting point for assessing the potential of such a device and paves the way for further investigation into their fundamental hydrodynamics.

F. Peak efficiency of a pair of wave-driven, rotating hydrofoils

The framework developed in Section II has been used to calculate the maximum hydrodynamic efficiency of a specific lift-based WEC in a variety of deep-water regular wave conditions. The device has been defined to consist of a pair of wave-driven rotating hydrofoils, each rotating about the common fixed point, O , with the same operational radius, R , and with an inter-hydrofoil phase difference of 180° (i.e., $\phi_2 - \phi_1 = 180^\circ$). The chord length of each hydrofoil is set to 6m and the submergence of the rotor, represented by the fixed common point, O , is set to 12m for all seas. Both hydrofoils are specified as NACA0012 profiles with lift and drag coefficients obtained from the software XFOIL [6]. In order to identify the maximum hydrodynamic efficiency, equation (27) has been implemented in Matlab [7] with the maximum value obtained through use of the *fminsearch* function. The rotor phase, individual hydrofoil pitch angles and the operational radius are all free to vary within the optimization function for each wave condition. Note that for this calculation, the upper limit of the operational radii during optimization is set equal to the distance from the fixed common point, O , to the lower bound of the wave trough in each wave climate (i.e., $R_{max} = h - a$).

The maximum hydrodynamic efficiency for the system operating in a variety of deep-water, 2-dimensional regular wave conditions is presented in Figure 3.

Figure 3: Peak hydrodynamic efficiency for a pair of 2-dimensional wave-driven, rotating hydrofoils operating in a variety of deep-water regular waves.

Inspection of the results reveals that hydrodynamic performance efficiencies in the range of 50% to 80% are possible within the range of wave heights and periods considered. This is promising as the results presented already include the impacts of drag losses. Even with the inclusion of those drag losses, the efficiency of the 2-dimensional lift-based WEC typically remains greater than the maximum efficiency of 50% achievable to the majority of traditional one degree-of-freedom WEC concepts in the absence of drag.

Inspection of Figure 3 reveals that the efficiency of the device is not constant with wave amplitude. Typically, it has been found that for this device type, the fundamental hydrodynamics dictate that the efficiency will increase with wave amplitude, which is in contrast to many traditional WECs. This increase in efficiency with amplitude is demonstrated in the mid-lower wave period region of Figure 3. However, from consideration of Figure 3 alone, it could be concluded that this pattern is invalidated as the wave period increases. Further inspection of results however reveals this reduction in efficiency with amplitude at higher wave periods to be a consequence of the specific device design parameters selected. In particular, this occurs as a result of the aforementioned radius limitation associated with hydrofoil surface-proximity. If the operational radius were not limited in this way, the downturn in performance at larger wave amplitudes would not occur, and the general trend of increasing efficiency with amplitude would be shown across the entire range of wave amplitudes. This effect becomes apparent when Figure 3 is considered in parallel with Figure 4 which presents the operational radii required to achieve the hydrodynamic efficiencies presented in Figure 3.

Figure 4: Operational radius required to achieve peak Capture Width Ratio

From inspection of Figure 4, it can be seen that the operational radius required to achieve maximum hydrodynamic efficiency increases with both wave amplitude and period, such that for the particular implementation presented, the operational radii eventually reach the surface proximity limit of $R \leq h - a$.

If a system with deeper submergence, variable submergence or variable chord length were employed, the severity of this effect can typically be reduced. However, this particular case has been presented to demonstrate the existence of the issue.

It is also noted that in practice, regions to the lower left of Figure 3 and Figure 4 are not attainable due to the physical and hydrodynamic limitations of a 6m chord length with very small operational radius. However, this occurs in parallel with a sharp decline in the hydrodynamic efficiency where wave periods are small (see results for $T < 6$ s in Figure 3). Fortunately, waves of very short period are typically of limited interest in wave energy owing to the small magnitudes of energy available for conversion and are infrequently encountered.

G. The effect of fixed operational radius

It is interesting to consider how system performance might vary for the case of sub-optimal specification of system design/control variables. Results for the case where the operational radius is no longer allowed to optimize, but rather is held fixed at 6m is presented in Figure 5.

Figure 5: Maximum efficiency for a pair of rotating hydrofoils with a 6m operational radius.

The results show that, as expected, the efficiency of the system across the range of sea states considered is reduced, however this reduction is typically moderate. Even with the fixed operational radius, hydrodynamic efficiencies in the range of 30% to greater than 70% remain possible in wave conditions of interest.

The limited drop in performance suggests that whilst control of the system's operational radius is evidently preferable to maximise power capture on at least a per-sea state basis, a lack of this functionality, or an imperfection in the application of that control, may be acceptable as reasonable optimisation remains possible through control of only hydrofoil pitch and phase if necessary.

A finding of greater concern for a fixed-radius system is the introduction of a 'minimum operating condition' as seen in the lower left-hand portion of Figure 5 where the system now fails to operate. This occurs due to drag-dominance of the system, resulting in a phenomenon

analogous to the cut-in-speed of a wind turbine. In essence, the greater the fixed operational radius of a wave-driven rotating hydrofoil, the higher the wave height and period required for system cut-in. This is not ideal as the hydrodynamic performance is therefore limited in small seas, which may form a significant portion of a typical scatter matrix.

This finding suggests that the ability to control the system radius to mitigate this occurrence would significantly increase the operational range of sea states within which a device could function, thus likely resulting in reduced system down time and an increased annual yield.

H. The effect of fixed operational radius & pitch

Figure 6 presents the hydrodynamic efficiency of the device where both the operational radius and hydrofoil pitch angles have been restricted from optimization.

Figure 6: Maximum efficiency for a pair of rotating hydrofoils with a 6m operational radius and hydrofoil pitch angles of -5° and $+5^\circ$.

As previous, a 6m fixed operational radius has been applied. In addition, a fixed pitch of -5° has been applied to the leading hydrofoil (described as being in the positive phase regime), and a fixed pitch of $+5^\circ$ has been applied to the lagging hydrofoil (described as being in the negative phase regime). For a more complete description of 'phase regime' the reader is referred to [8]. These values of pitch were selected as they represent the approximate centroid of the range of pitch angles required to achieve the maximum efficiencies presented with the fixed operational radius of 6m (Figure 5). Pitch angles required to generate the efficiencies presented for the case of fixed operational radius ranged from approximately $(\pm)1^\circ$ to $(\pm)9^\circ$, hence the specific fixed pitch angles selected.

Results for the case of fixed radius and pitch show that there is not a significant further reduction in performance compared to the case where only the radius is restricted. This suggests that under operational conditions, if a suitable phase can be maintained, or if the sensitivity of performance to variations in rotor phase is not severe, then imperfection in specification of hydrofoil pitch might not result in significant loss of power capture beyond the case

of a fixed operational radius. Indeed, it can be seen that even with fixing both the radius and pitch at sub-optimal conditions, the device will still operate and produce significant quantities of useful energy output across the majority of the wave conditions considered. This might suggest reasonable system stability, even in the absence of perfect control. However, it should be noted that in the absence of phase locking this would not be possible, as hydrofoil pitch angles must change direction depending on whether the hydrofoil is in the 180° of phase leading or lagging the wave. This requirement for alternate direction of pitch requirement dependent on phase occurs due to the local directionality of lift force generation depending on whether the hydrofoil leads or lags the wave in terms of its positional phase. For more discussion on this and the implications of phase regime the reader is again referred to [8].

I. Sensitivity with phase and radius

The previous two sections considered variability in performance across various seas for a device with limited ability to adapt its operational radius and hydrofoil pitch angles. The results showed some, but not severe reduction in power capture.

It is also useful to consider performance variation in a given sea due to deviation of control/design variables, and in particular with regard to the impact of phase. It also seems insightful to consider the sensitivity due to deviation of the operational radius from the ideal, as it is likely that hydrofoil pitch control will be less challenging to implement mechanically. Note however this does not imply the development of an appropriate pitch control strategy to be a trivial matter.

When consideration of system performance variation in a given sea with radius and phase is combined with the previous ‘per sea-state’ assessments, the results may begin to provide an understanding of the expected stability of a lift-based WEC’s potential performance in irregular seas or with imperfect control.

The sensitivity of the performance of a two-hydrofoil system to variation in the operational radius and rotor-wave phase relationship is presented in Figure 7. The results presented are for the case of device operation in a regular sea of 10s period and 1m wave amplitude. Note that the rotor phase is reported according to the phase for the first hydrofoil, and the second hydrofoil will be 180° out of phase with the first, as in all previous cases. Also note that results are only presented for rotor phase ranging from 0° to 180° for ease of inspection, as results are symmetrical across 0° . Finally, the system was permitted to optimize pitch in each case considered in the generation of Figure 7.

Figure 7 shows that, as expected, the system achieves maximum performance at a particular radius and phase, with reducing performance as each variable deviates from its optimum. The range of both radius and phase at which near-maximum performance is achieved is promising,

with a broad peak observed. This indicates the system is relatively insensitive to imperfect operational control/design conditions near the peak for the given wave condition. This is found to be generally true for other cases which have been considered with reasonable device characteristics. Furthermore, it is promising to note the majority of conditions result in useful power capture. This suggests that even when the system is poorly ‘tuned’, useful energy can still be extracted and the chance of stall or generation of zero net driving force is small as long as hydrofoils do not cross into opposing phase regimes, or if they do, that a flip of the pitch direction occurs.

Figure 7: Maximum efficiency for a pair of rotating hydrofoils operating in a regular sea with $T=10s$, $a=1m$ with variation in rotor phase and operational radius.

Indeed, for any particular case, the driving torque only approaches zero when its phase relative to the wave approaches either 0° or 180° . This is to be expected and is driven by the loss of any angle of attack relative to the tangent which in turn results in the generation of a lift force in the radial direction. Under such conditions, no component of the lift force generated acts in the tangential direction and so lift cannot act to drive the system. Thus, the reason for the drop in power capture as the system approaches a phase of either 0° or 180° is due to the increase in drag dominance over lift.

Furthermore, it has been found that for systems with a non-dimensional radius, χ , ($\chi = R/a$) much greater than unity, it tends to be the case that positive drive is always generated by the system except at, or very close to phase angles of 0° and 180° as explained. As the non-dimensional radius decreases towards or below unity, the area in which no drive torque is generated increases. Fortunately, for systems with a small number of hydrofoils, maximum efficiency is typically achieved when the non-dimensional radius is much greater than unity, suggesting that systems designed appropriately for given deployment conditions should not suffer significantly from this effect. Indeed, even in very large seas with individual wave heights of 4-5m, this should not become a noticeable issue for expected device designs. It would be expected however that the

smaller the non-dimensional radius, χ , the greater the sensitivity may be to imperfections in control/design.

In addition, the use of larger operational radii is associated with a reduced influence of the wave-induced velocity on the relative inflow velocity and more stable angle of attack values. This further supports the insensitive nature of the system assuming phase locking is at least weakly maintained. The potential influence of swiftly changing wave-to-wave characteristics such as those experienced in irregular seas has not yet been investigated, however this work is ongoing.

Another way to encourage the system to favour larger non-dimensional radii is to reduce the chord length of the hydrofoils. However, the greater the radius required, the greater the submergence must also be, and likely the greater the absolute range of radii required to seek a per-sea state optimization. It is therefore evident that a balance must be sought between all the various design and control variables and conditions. However, it is promising to note that the system appears relatively insensitive to the control conditions across a variety of wave conditions suggesting it is possible that in the worst case of no achievable instantaneous control of system characteristics, reasonable power capture should still be possible so long as placement in the appropriate phase regime is achievable.

IV. CONCLUSION

A mathematical framework has been developed which calculates the hydrodynamic performance of a lift-based WEC consisting of any number of 2-dimensional rotating hydrofoils operating in regular waves. The framework was used to calculate the maximum power capture for a given implementation of such a device. In particular, the hydrodynamic efficiency, defined as the percentage of power captured from the incident waves, was calculated for a device consisting of two rotating hydrofoils with equal operational radii and operating 180° out of phase with one another. The axis of rotation was assumed fixed at a submergence depth of 12m, and each hydrofoil was defined as a NACA0012 profile with 6m chord length.

Results were presented which show the maximum power capture for the system ranged from approximately 50% to 80% across a range of waves with height and period characteristics similar to those expected to represent the statistical majority of those experienced in energetic deployment locations such as coastlines along the North Atlantic. These values were potentially possible when the system was permitted to optimise operational radius, phase, and pitch on a per wave-climate basis.

It was shown that device performance declines when the system is restricted from optimization of these control/design variables, however not severely so. With both radius and pitch held fixed across wave conditions at 6m and $(\pm)5^\circ$ respectively, hydrodynamic efficiencies ranging from 30% to 70% were still potentially possible in the range of wave conditions of interest. It was also shown that the range of operational radii and rotor phase across

which close to maximum power capture is obtained for a given sea, is relatively large. This suggests that the system is not highly sensitive to imperfections in deviations of design and control variables from their optima when the overall design is reasonable. Consequently, it is proposed that system performance in irregular seas, even in the absence of significant control should be reasonable if approximate phase locking can be maintained.

Finally, it is noted that the mathematics developed which describe the performance of the device are strikingly similar to those for more traditional Wave Energy Converter concepts. It is therefore hoped that many of the methods and tools currently employed by the industry could be readily adapted to suit the assessment of lift-based systems.

These findings combined suggest that lift-based WECs consisting of a number of wave-driven hydrofoils likely represent a reasonable alternative to more traditional wave energy converter concepts. Further work is ongoing.

V. FURTHER WORK

The work presented in this conference paper is only the beginning of hydrodynamic investigations into lift-based WECs. There is still a significant amount of work to be completed to develop a complete understanding of the hydrodynamics of lift-based WECs. At present, work is ongoing in Queen's University Belfast to develop further insight into the fundamental hydrodynamics.

In common with many wave energy converters, performance in irregular seas will depend on the ability of the control strategy to maintain optimum operating conditions. However, the results presented in this work suggest that lift-based WECs are reasonably insensitive to operating conditions, which may reduce control requirements for lift-based WECs in irregular seas. Work is ongoing to consider the potential performance in more realistic environments including the performance in irregular seas.

Work is also ongoing to develop further understanding of the hydrodynamics for finite span devices. Preliminary results obtained at this stage suggest that capture width ratios for finite span, lift-based WECs can typically exceed unity across wide ranges of wave conditions due to their exploitation of the point absorber effect, however further discussion of this finding is beyond the scope of this introductory paper.

Beyond the hydrodynamics, the entire range of typical wave energy research topics remain largely unexplored for lift based WECs. This includes areas such as structural analysis, numerical modelling, physical experimentation, device control, power systems engineering, operations & maintenance, environmental & social acceptance, cost of energy, market analysis, etc. Whilst some of these are the subjects of ongoing investigations [9]–[11], there is clearly a very significant amount of work still to be done to develop a complete understanding of the design, installation, operation and adoption of lift-based WECs.

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